

Food Recommendation Using Machine Learning

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Abstract—The recommendation system will help users to figure out a decision on selection of right combinations of food. The system makes recommendations on prior likely experience. The proposed system recommends the food item that mostly be eaten with the searched food item. This system is very helpful as most of the people still have confusions on what food is to be eaten in combinations with a main course. It may lead to customers having bad experience as they don't choose the apt combinations. So food recommendation system helps to identify healthy and likely food item that mostly appeals to the selected main course. It is done with the help of methods like K Nearest Neighbour, content based filtering etc.

Keywords—food recommendation, voice assistance, food combinations, K Nearest Neighbour algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

In this modern era, most of the people are in search of new technologies and informations. In addition, most of the traditional methodologies also turned to online modes as in case of buying and selling of goods and services. And for some cases, this change of mode from offline to online has made great changes or may be some services has become more efficient while online.

But in case of restaurants both modes are efficient as customer choose the restaurant as per their interests. Also customers will look for factors like quality food, services, cleanliness, ratings etc.

But recommendations or reviews bad bought quite a lot of changes as if a customer tries out a new dish and the user likes it then they review the dish and make the reviews available online so that everyone gets to know about the dish and thereby giving the restaurant an extra boost.

In this proposed system, different combination of food items is recommended as the customer selects a main course. Recommendation is done on the basis of ratings from previous customer. While recommending a voice assistance is also provided so that it could help the customer who are blind or illiterate to choose the right combinations as per the main course selected. Now recommendation is important as some customers struggle to find the right combinations. For example: Porotto and Beef, Tapiocca and Fish.

If a customer places an order for porotto and got confused with what combinations nice with it, then this recommendation system comes into action by recommending the best available combination with porotto. The recommendation system always plays a vital role in picking up the right combination food item as per earlier ratings. This system which on the basis of K Nearest Neighbour algorithm and content based filtering. Thus the proposed system fulfils each individuals fooding experiences in the restaurant.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Junan Pan et al. [1] A recommender system that help filterate the information and provide users by relevant information. Users interest model would be found out based on the previous historical records in the restaurant. The representation of restaurant recommendation system based on deep learning and other subtles under machine learning. The features are carried out by convolutional neural network and logistic regression model. That will be used to calculate the matching probability between the recall set and test set.

Mohammad Salehan et al. [2] The researches represent that majority of the consumer's read online review to took up a decision. It should not only give suggestion or feedback; but also it will affect brand, sales and revenue. A vast amount of reviews could be carried out to different services or products. The proposed research was used content based filtering recommender system that examines and make numeric score to taste of each restaurant.

Sadha Kodali et al. [3] Restaurant Recommendation System by finding out restaurant from cast amount of resources around. The recommendation will be obtained by the search of user cuisine. Top rated restaurants will be recommended to the consumers according with the rating. The recommended restaurant system filters and emphasize the suggestions with tasty and quality restaurants. This proposed system can be carried out by K-Nearest Neighbor algorithm with mapreduce paradigm. The system will helpful to any people who visits unknown place and for finding out best restaurants in that area.

Sathya Seelan K et al. [4] The individuals will highly depend on recommendation systems in a new place. Food

quality and services offered on the restaurant are mostly interested and attracted by the customers. Recommendation should obtain with service rating and food rating. The result of proposed system is to be taken forward to most popular restaurant. The proposed system is implemented by K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm and multiclass SUM classification.

Amanuel Melese et al. [5] The new technologies are not much familiar in food sector that could compared with other sections. The proposed system recommends restaurants and foods using hybrid filtering system. Hybrid mechanism used to make preferences to the user. The recommendations will be done with the user interests. Full functionalities could be provided with content based filtering and collaborative filtering method. The proposed system is implemented with machine learning algorithm like random forest, linear regression, gradient boosting and K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm.

III. METHODOLOGY

The following questions have been addressed by the proposed Recommendation system using statistical techniques and exploratory data analysis to learn about the various unique combinations and recipes.

The number of user ratings, the total number of times the food has been evaluated, and the distribution of ratings for food, service, and quality individually were all discovered for the system recommendation.

Data Selection

The primary data source for this recommendation system is from GitHub, which will be used in this application to suggest meal pairings.

It includes meals and ratings in 2 csv files altogether. In that, we evaluate the rating file, which mostly consists of 3 attributes and 510 instances. include a food file with 310 occurrences and primarily 5 attributes. This dataset is connected with our application so that the machine learning algorithm can provide the customer-appropriate outcomes.

Food_ID	Name	C_Type	Veg_Non	Describe
1	summer sc	Healthy Fc	veg	white balsamic vinegar, lemon juice, lemon rind, red chillies, garlic cloves (crushed), olive oil, si
2	chicken mi	Healthy Fc	non-veg	olive oil, chicken mince, garlic (minced), onion, salt, black pepper, carrot, cabbage, green onion
3	sweet chili	Snack	veg	almonds whole, egg white, curry leaves, salt, sugar (fine grain), red chili powder
4	tricolour s	Healthy Fc	veg	vinegar, honey/sugar, soy sauce, salt, garlic: cloves (minced), chilli pepper (sliced), green papaya
5	christmas	Dessert	veg	christmas dry fruits (pre-soaked), orange zest, lemon zest, jaggery syrup, almond flour, apple, b
6	japanese c	Japanese	veg	japanese curry, sticky rice, cheese inside rice, barley salka, wasabi mayo, red capsicum cube (c
7	chocolate	Dessert	veg	almonds, eggs, granulated sugar, bittersweet chocolate, unsalted butter, flour, baking powder,
8	lamb and	Healthy Fc	non-veg	lamb bones (preferably shank and shoulder), onions, celery, ginger, garlic, carrot, chargrilled ve
9	cream of a	Healthy Fc	veg	vegetable stock, skimmed milk, toasted almonds (powdered), butter, flour, salt and pepper, nu
10	broccoli ar	Healthy Fc	veg	vegetable stock, broccoli, ground almonds (toasted), skimmed milk, salt, freshly ground black p
11	coconut li	Healthy Fc	veg	uncooked quinoa, water, red onion, cucumber (diced), purple cabbage, avocado (ripened and c
12	lemon hot	Snack	non-veg	young corn on the cob, honey, lemon juice, garlic cloves (smashed), celery stalk, chives, carrot,
13	watermel	Healthy Fc	veg	fresh strawberries, honey, low fat yogurt, watermelon, chia seeds
14	peach, ras	Healthy Fc	veg	fresh raspberries, ripe banana, almond, fresh peach slices, low fat yogurt, fresh raspberry, pea
15	almond an	Indian	veg	almond flakes, onion, poha, cranberries (frozen/ dried), salt, oil, curry leaves, green chillies, fres
16	almond an	Indian	veg	almond silvers, raw banana (boiled), almond paste, cooking cream, refined oil, mace powder, c
17	baked nam	Snack	veg	almonds (crushed), tomato, garlic cloves, basil sprig, lemon, salt, pepper, for namak para; refin
18	grilled alm	Dessert	veg	khoya, sweetener (optional), almonds (crushed)
19	baked shai	Snack	veg	whole wheat flour (atta), refined flour (maida), garlic cloves (crushed), salt, red chilli powder, c
20	baked ml	Snack	veg	oats, ragi flour (bhakri atta), wheat flour, rice flour, urad dal flour (dry roast and grind the dal t
21	apple rabd	Dessert	veg	apples, milk, sugar, green cardamoms, almonds (blanched), pistachios (blanched)
22	baked nam	Snack	veg	whole wheat flour (atta), refined flour (maida), baking powder, ghee, salt, carom seeds (ajwain
23	dates and	Dessert	veg	dates (pitted), mixed nuts (almonds, cashews, walnuts, pistachios, peanuts), desiccated coconu
24	green lent	Dessert	veg	whole moong beans, cow ghee, raisins, whole milk, jaggery (organic), ground cardamom, almoi
25	cashew nu	Dessert	veg	cashew paste, ghee, khanda (a sweetening agent and a healthier substitute of sugar), flax or ch
26	almond pe	Snack	veg	toasted almonds, blueberries, oats, corn flakes, olive oil, salt, curry leaves, mustard seeds, cum

Fig. 1

User_ID	Food_ID	Rating
1	88	4
1	46	3
1	24	5
1	25	4
2	49	1
2	33	8
2	106	9
2	71	8
3	73	9
3	110	10
3	168	1
3	201	8
3	209	6
3	46	2
3	65	3
3	292	8
3	299	1
4	14	5
4	141	5
4	170	1
4	212	10
4	128	6
4	21	1
5	52	9
5	64	2
5	198	10
5	241	9
5	8	6

Fig.2

Basis of Recommendation

This is the standard starting point strategy. This methodology does not emphasise a personalised approach; instead, it only suggests to the user the most well-liked item in that restaurant, at that time. As a result, the consumer may have used the product in the past or may not have. It suggests things that are currently popular or trending in that restaurant based on the ratings.

When we don't have any prior historical information on the specific food, this kind of recommendation is quite helpful. It functions according to the popular theory and the current fashion. The system's shortcomings include the fact that it is not individualised and may provide each consumer the same recommendations for products depending upon query of food item.

```
def food_recommendation(Food_Name):
    n = 10
    FoodList = food[food['Name'].str.contains(Food_Name)]
    if len(FoodList):
        Foodi = FoodList.iloc[0]['Food_ID']
        Foodi = dataset[dataset['Food_ID'] == Foodi].index[0]
        distances , indices = model.kneighbors(csr_dataset[Foodi],n_neighbors=n+1)
        Food_indices = sorted(list(zip(indices,squeeze(),tolist()),distances.squeeze(),tolist()),key=lambda x: x[1])[0:-1]
        Recommendations = []
        for val in Food_indices:
            Foodi = dataset.iloc[val[0]]['Food_ID']
            i = food[food['Food_ID'] == Foodi].index
            Recommendations.append({'Name':food.iloc[i]['Name'].values[0],'Distance':val[1]})
        df = pd.DataFrame(Recommendations,index=range(1,n+1))
        print(df['Name'])
        speak("most suitable dish for you is "+ df['Name'])
    else:
        print("No Similar Foods.")
        speak("No similar Foods ")

food = pd.read_csv("D:/Food-Recommendation-System-master/food.csv")
ratings = pd.read_csv("D:/Food-Recommendation-System-master/ratings.csv")
dataset = ratings.pivot_table(index='Food_ID',columns='User_ID',values='Rating')
dataset.fillna(0,inplace=True)
csr_dataset = csr_matrix(dataset.values)
dataset.reset_index(inplace=True)

model = NearestNeighbors(metric='cosine', algorithm='brute', n_neighbors=20, n_jobs=-1)
model.fit(csr_dataset)
fooditem = input("Enter your Food item")
food_recommendation(fooditem)
```

Fig.3

Content based filtering

Systems that make product recommendations to users based on the product's description and the user's interest profile. Systems for recommending web pages, news articles, restaurants, television shows, and merchandise are all examples of content-based recommendation systems in use. A method for describing the items that may be recommended, a method for building a user profile that describes the kinds of items the user likes, and a method for comparing items to the user profile to decide what to recommend are all shared by content-based recommendation systems, despite the fact that the specifics of various systems vary. When the user provides comment on the desirability of products that have been offered to them, the profile is frequently automatically constructed and updated.

An exclusive class of information filtering systems are recommender systems. Information filtering, which may be thought of as a categorization task, deals with the delivery of information chosen from a big collection that the user is likely to find interesting or useful. Here it filtrates the food item upon the customer query. It shows up most likely food combinations or recipes present on the restaurant.

```
dataset = ratings.pivot_table(index='Food_ID', columns='User_ID', values='Rating')
dataset.fillna(0, inplace=True)
csr_dataset = csr_matrix(dataset.values)
dataset.reset_index(inplace=True)
```

Fig.4

Algorithms

Python is being used in this paper's machine learning algorithm. This due to mostly due to Python's extensive machine learning support packages. Here, the algorithm used is K Nearest Neighbour algorithm for the recommendations made.

Altered the feature space of users by mapping each attribute they had that was specific to a business to a particular business cluster using the findings from KNN clustering on food item. This allowed us to make sure that the majority of user pairs had at least one business cluster in common that they had both rated, which ultimately made it possible for us to determine user similarity more precisely. In order to categorise the users into clusters of similar users using a similarity function based on the similarity of the ratings, we performed k-nearest neighbours with 10-fold cross validation on the users after creating this new input feature space of users.

Using this final model, make suggestions for a user by projecting ratings in a similar way on all companies that the user hasn't yet rated, then output the ones that result in the highest rating%.

```
model = NearestNeighbors(metric='cosine', algorithm='brute', n_neighbors=20, n_jobs=-1)
model.fit(csr_dataset)
fooditem = input("Enter your Food item")
food_recommendation(fooditem)
```

Fig.5

Text-to-Speech Conversion Library

A Python text-to-speech conversion library is called pyttsx3. It is compatible with Python 2 and 3 and works offline, unlike competing libraries. To obtain a reference to a pyttsx3. Engine instance, an application calls the pyttsx3.init() factory method. It is a very user-friendly programme that turns typed text into speech. Here the system used for the voice assistance by text-to-speech conversion library in python. While recommending a voice assistance is also provided so that it could help the customer who are blind or illiterate to choose the right combination as per the main food item selected.

```
engine = pyttsx3.init()

def speak(audio):
    engine.say(audio)
    engine.runAndWait()

speak('Welcome to Food Recommendation system')
```

Fig.6

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed system provides a recommendation to the customer for food combinations. It helps to find out a healthy and good combination of food items. The goal is to develop a system that uses machine learning to create food recommendation system with voice assistance. This helps the customers to choose the combinations of food items based on the recommendation. Voice assistance will help the customers who are illiterate or blind. This provide a lot of help to choose their apt food item with its best combination. The recommendation is carried out upon by the ratings provided by previous customers. This paper is able to make more future scopes too. Rating is done by using machine learning algorithms and techniques. It also depicts the graphical analysis carried out in future.

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